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Israfilov Doston Omonulla o'g'li
English Teacher, Perfect University
E-mail: israfilovdoston@gmail.com

PRINCIPLES FOR DETERMINING INTERLEVEL GRAMMATICAL MINIMUMS IN
TEACHING UZBEK TO ENGLISH SPEAKERS

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to developing the scientific and methodological foundations for determining interlevel grammatical minimums in teaching Uzbek to English-speaking learners. The relevance of the study is determined by the growing interest in learning Uzbek as a foreign language and the need to create effective methodological models that ensure the gradual development of learners' grammatical competence in accordance with the CEFR proficiency levels. Although linguodidactic research in the field of foreign language teaching has been developing rapidly, the issue of scientifically selecting and distributing Uzbek grammatical material across proficiency levels remains insufficiently explored.

The article analyzes the factors influencing the acquisition of Uzbek grammar by English-speaking learners. The author substantiates the importance of the functional-semantic approach in the selection of grammatical material. A model for the gradual acquisition of grammatical structures is proposed, ranging from basic communicative means at the A1 level to complex syntactic and pragmatic constructions at the B2–C1 levels.

Keywords: interlevel grammatical minimum, competence, communicative approach, functional-semantic approach, comparative linguistic analysis, language interference, CEFR levels

Israfilov Doston Omonulla o'g'li
Perfect-university ingliz tili o'qituvchisi
E-mail: israfilovdoston@gmail.com

O'ZBEK TILINI INGLIZZABONLARGA O'QITISHDA DARAJALARARO
GRAMMATIK MINIMUMLARNI BELGILASH ASOSLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqola inglizzabon o'quvchilarga o'zbek tilini o'qitishda darajalararo grammatik minimumlarni belgilashning ilmiy-metodik asoslarini ishlab chiqishga bag'ishlangan. Tadqiqotning dolzarbligi o'zbek tilini xorijiy til sifatida o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqishning ortib borayotgani hamda o'quvchilarning grammatik kompetensiyasini CEFR xalqaro darajalariga muvofiq bosqichma-bosqich shakllantirishni ta'minlaydigan samarali metodik modellarni yaratish zarurati bilan belgilanadi. Chet tillarni o'qitish sohasida lingvodidaktik tadqiqotlar jadal rivojlanayotgan bo'lsa-da, o'zbek tili grammatik materialini darajalar bo'yicha ilmiy asosda saralash va taqsimlash masalasi yetarlicha ishlab chiqilmagan.

Maqolada inglizabon o‘quvchilar tomonidan o‘zbek tili grammatikasini o‘zlashtirishga ta’sir etuvchi omillar tahlil qilingan. Muallif tomonidan grammatik materialni tanlashda funksional-semantik yondashuvning ahamiyati asoslab berilgan. Maqolada A1 darajasidagi asosiy kommunikativ vositalardan tortib, B2–C1 darajalaridagi murakkab sintaktik va pragmatik konstruksiyalargacha bo‘lgan grammatik materialni bosqichma-bosqich o‘zlashtirish modeli taklif etilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Darajalararo grammatik minimum, kompetentlik, kommunikativ yondashuv, funksional-semantik yondashuv, qiyosiy-lingvistik tahlil, til interferensiyasi, lingvodidaktika, CEFR darajalari.

Исрафилов Достон Омонулла угли

Преподаватель английского языка, Perfect University

E-mail: israfilovdoston@gmail.com

ПРИНЦИПЫ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ МЕЖУРОВНЕВОГО ГРАММАТИЧЕСКОГО МИНИМУМА ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ УЗБЕКСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ АНГЛОЯЗЫЧНЫХ УЧАЩИХСЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена разработке научно-методических основ определения межуровневого грамматического минимума при обучении узбекскому языку англоязычных учащихся. Актуальность исследования обусловлена возрастающим интересом к изучению узбекского языка как иностранного, а также необходимостью создания эффективных методических моделей, обеспечивающих поэтапное формирование грамматической компетенции обучающихся в соответствии с международными уровнями владения языком CEFR. Несмотря на активное развитие лингводидактических исследований в области преподавания иностранных языков, проблема научно обоснованного отбора и распределения грамматического материала по уровням владения узбекским языком остается недостаточно разработанной.

В статье анализируются факторы, влияющие на усвоение грамматики узбекского языка англоязычными учащимися. Обосновывается значимость функционально-семантического подхода при отборе грамматического материала. Предлагается модель поэтапного освоения грамматических структур — от базовых коммуникативных средств уровня A1 до сложных синтаксических и прагматических конструкций уровней B2–C1.

Ключевые слова: межуровневый грамматический минимум, компетенция, коммуникативный подход, функционально-семантический подход, сопоставительно-лингвистический анализ, языковая интерференция, уровни CEFR

Introduction and relevance of the topic. In contemporary language teaching methodology, the selection of instructional materials, their systematization according to proficiency levels, and their adaptation to the educational process constitute one of the most pressing methodological issues. In particular, the question of how grammatical knowledge should be presented in teaching Uzbek to English-speaking learners – in terms of scope, sequence, and underlying criteria – represents a complex linguo-methodological task. In practice, grammatical materials are frequently selected on the basis of existing textbooks, teachers’ professional experience, or general methodological perspectives. Such an approach may result in insufficient consistency within the instructional process and, in certain cases, may lead either to excessive cognitive burden or to the omission of essential grammatical units.

One of the principal aspects of this issue is that although the concept of a “grammatical minimum” is widely employed in language teaching practice, its precise linguo-methodological criteria across proficiency levels (A1 – C1) have not yet been sufficiently elaborated. The absence of a unified scientific framework for distributing instructional materials according to language levels gives rise to diverse approaches, thereby complicating the step-by-step development of learners’

communicative competence. Furthermore, the typological, grammatical, and structural differences between English and Uzbek directly influence learners' acquisition of a new grammatical system. For this reason, the process of determining grammatical minimums requires not only a linguistic but also a cognitive approach. Learners' processes of perceiving, processing, and applying language are closely connected with psycholinguistic factors. Consequently, the selection and systematization of grammatical materials necessitate taking into account cognitive load and stages of language acquisition. From this perspective, developing the scientific foundations for determining level-based grammatical minimums in teaching Uzbek to English-speaking learners constitutes a pressing methodological task.

Methods and level of previous research. In the present study, the issue of determining level-based grammatical minimums in teaching Uzbek to English-speaking learners was analyzed through a comprehensive methodological approach. The research methods employed included theoretical analysis, comparative linguistic analysis, the functional approach, and pedagogical observation. In determining grammatical minimums, not only their formal structure but also their communicative function and practical significance for learners were regarded as the principal criteria.

At the initial stage of the research, scholarly literature related to foreign language teaching methodology was analyzed. In particular, theoretical perspectives concerning the concept of grammatical minimums, their role in the educational process, and their distribution across proficiency levels were examined. Within this process, the communicative approach, competence-based education, and theories of functional grammar served as the principal methodological foundations. These approaches require attention to the actual use of grammatical units in communicative activity when selecting instructional material [1].

At the subsequent stage, the grammatical systems of Uzbek and English were subjected to comparative analysis. This analysis was aimed at identifying grammatical phenomena that create difficulties for English-speaking learners. In particular, the differences between the analytical nature and rigid word order of English and the agglutinative structure, suffixation system, and relatively flexible word order of Uzbek were examined in detail. On this basis, the criteria of "degree of complexity" and "communicative necessity" were integrated in determining grammatical minimums [2].

During the course of the research, the functional-semantic approach also occupied an important place. According to this approach, grammatical units are selected not according to their formal characteristics, but according to their function in speech. For example, at the beginner levels, tense forms necessary for everyday communication, possessive suffixes, and simple sentence constructions are considered priorities for learners. At higher levels, however, complex syntactic structures, conditional mood forms, and subordinate clauses are introduced gradually and systematically. This ensures the consistent and systematic acquisition of grammatical material.

Furthermore, elements of pedagogical observation and practical experimentation were also employed in the study. Classroom activities conducted with English-speaking learners studying Uzbek were analyzed in order to determine which grammatical units were acquired more rapidly and which created greater difficulties. The results of these observations served to substantiate the theoretical conclusions from a practical perspective.

With regard to the level of previous research on the topic, it can be observed that the issue of grammatical minimums in foreign language teaching has been extensively studied at the international level. In particular, various approaches to the selection and distribution of grammatical material according to proficiency levels have been developed in the teaching of English and other European languages [3]. However, within the framework of teaching Uzbek as a foreign language, this issue has not yet been sufficiently systematized. Existing studies on Uzbek grammar have largely been presented in a general descriptive manner, while the problem of their differential distribution across learning levels has received comparatively limited attention. Although certain methodological studies attempt to simplify grammatical materials, they often fail to adequately take into account learners' linguistic background, particularly the influence of English [4].

Furthermore, there are almost no specialized curricula or grammatical minimum systems specifically designed for English-speaking learners. This may result in the excessive or illogical distribution of grammatical material within the instructional process. From this perspective, the present study arises from the necessity of scientifically determining, systematizing, and implementing level-based grammatical minimums in the teaching of Uzbek.

In our view, the comprehensive nature of the methods employed in this research, together with the insufficient level of prior investigation into the topic, constitutes the scientific novelty of the study. The proposed approach contributes to the effective teaching of Uzbek to English-speaking learners, the gradual acquisition of grammatical material, and the optimization of instructional curricula.

Discussion. The findings of the present study demonstrate that the issue of determining level-based grammatical minimums in teaching Uzbek to English-speaking learners requires not only methodological, but also linguodidactic and empirical approaches. Although the principle of presenting grammatical material from simple to complex has traditionally been regarded as one of the fundamental approaches in foreign language teaching, the results of this research indicate that such a principle cannot always ensure effective language acquisition. The complexity of grammatical units should not be understood solely in terms of their formal or structural characteristics. Rather, grammatical difficulty is also shaped by the learner's prior linguistic experience, cognitive perception, native language system, and the typological differences between the native and target languages. Therefore, in establishing level-based grammatical minimums, it becomes necessary to reconsider the very notion of "grammatical complexity" from a broader linguodidactic perspective.

The study further reveals that, for English-speaking learners, the agglutinative nature of Uzbek constitutes one of the most significant challenges in the process of grammatical acquisition. In English, grammatical meaning is frequently conveyed through auxiliary words, prepositions, and relatively strict syntactic structures. In contrast, Uzbek primarily expresses grammatical relations through suffixation, where multiple grammatical meanings may be attached to a single lexical stem. As a result, learners often experience difficulty in comprehending and producing grammatical forms in which tense, person, possession, modality, and negation are simultaneously represented within one morphological structure. From a psycholinguistic perspective, such forms impose a greater cognitive burden on learners whose native language belongs to an analytical language system.

This challenge becomes particularly evident in the Uzbek verbal system. In many cases, tense forms, mood markers, person-number indicators, and negative constructions function together within a single verbal unit, producing morphologically complex patterns unfamiliar to English-speaking learners. During the research process, it was observed that learners frequently experienced confusion when attempting to distinguish between grammatical categories that are represented separately in English but simultaneously encoded in Uzbek morphology. Consequently, the results of the study confirm the necessity of minimizing grammatical overload at the beginner levels and introducing only those grammatical structures that are functionally essential for elementary communication. Such an approach contributes not only to reducing learners' cognitive difficulties, but also to strengthening communicative confidence during the early stages of language acquisition.

Another important issue identified in the course of the research concerns the influence of syntactic interference arising from differences in word order between English and Uzbek. English predominantly follows a rigid SVO (subject-verb-object) sentence structure, whereas Uzbek generally employs an SOV (subject-object-verb) pattern. This typological distinction frequently leads learners to transfer English syntactic models directly into Uzbek speech production. As observed during classroom analysis and pedagogical observation, English-speaking learners often attempt to position the verb immediately after the subject, following English sentence construction patterns. Such interference results in grammatically inaccurate or stylistically unnatural Uzbek sentences.

From this perspective, the study demonstrates that the determination of grammatical minimums should not be limited exclusively to morphological categories. Equal attention must also be devoted to the gradual teaching of syntactic structures and sentence-building patterns. At the beginner levels, learners should first acquire the most communicatively necessary sentence models through repetitive and functional usage. More complex syntactic constructions, including subordinate

clauses, conditional structures, and extended sentence patterns, should only be introduced progressively at higher levels of proficiency. This staged approach ensures systematic language acquisition and prevents excessive grammatical burden during the initial stages of learning.

The findings of the study also highlight the importance of adopting a functional-semantic approach in the selection and distribution of grammatical material. Traditional grammar-oriented instruction frequently prioritizes the formal presentation of grammatical rules, whereas the present research demonstrates that learners achieve more effective results when grammatical units are introduced according to their communicative value and practical relevance. In this regard, grammatical structures that are essential for everyday interaction, self-expression, asking questions, and maintaining basic communication should receive priority at lower proficiency levels. Such a communicative orientation allows learners to use grammatical knowledge actively rather than merely memorizing abstract grammatical paradigms.

Furthermore, the pedagogical observations conducted during the research indicate that English-speaking learners acquire grammatical structures more successfully when they are presented within meaningful communicative contexts rather than in isolation. Context-based instruction enables learners to associate grammatical forms with practical language use, thereby facilitating retention and reducing cognitive difficulty. This observation further supports the view that grammatical minimums should be determined not only according to linguistic criteria, but also in accordance with psycholinguistic and communicative considerations.

The level-based grammatical minimum model proposed in this study is grounded in a functional-semantic approach. According to this approach, each grammatical unit is selected on the basis of its communicative function and practical relevance within real speech situations. In other words, grammatical structures are not introduced merely because they belong to the formal grammatical system of the language, but because they enable learners to perform specific communicative tasks. Such an approach places communicative effectiveness at the center of grammatical instruction and seeks to align grammatical progression with learners' actual language needs.

For example, at the A1 level, learners require only those grammatical tools that enable them to introduce themselves, express basic personal information, satisfy elementary communicative needs, and participate in simple everyday interactions. At this stage, a minimal set of tense forms, possessive suffixes, personal pronouns, question patterns, and simple sentence structures is considered sufficient. The emphasis is placed not on grammatical completeness, but on communicative functionality. Consequently, learners are introduced only to those grammatical structures that are immediately applicable in practical communication. This approach reduces unnecessary cognitive burden and allows learners to gain confidence in using the target language from the earliest stages of instruction.

At the A2 and B1 levels, however, communicative needs gradually expand, and as a result the grammatical system also becomes more complex. At these intermediate stages, learners begin to express more sophisticated meanings related to time, condition, causality, and personal opinion. Therefore, past tense forms, conditional mood constructions, causal connectors, comparative structures, and subordinate clauses are introduced progressively and systematically. The gradual incorporation of these grammatical units ensures continuity in language development and prevents abrupt increases in grammatical difficulty. Such staged progression also contributes to the development of learners' communicative competence by enabling them to participate in more elaborate and contextually varied forms of interaction.

At higher proficiency levels, stylistic and pragmatic aspects of language use become increasingly important. At this stage, grammatical instruction extends beyond structural accuracy and focuses on the learner's ability to adapt language according to context, intention, and discourse conventions. Learners are expected not only to construct grammatically correct sentences, but also to select appropriate grammatical forms in accordance with social, stylistic, and communicative factors. Thus, grammatical competence at advanced levels becomes closely connected with pragmatic and discourse competence.

One of the principal advantages of the proposed model is that it distributes grammatical material in accordance with learners' real communicative needs without creating excessive instructional overload. Rather than presenting large quantities of grammatical information simultaneously, the model prioritizes the gradual and purposeful introduction of functionally necessary structures. This approach positively affects learner motivation and facilitates the practical application of grammatical knowledge in authentic communication. The findings obtained during the research process demonstrate that selecting grammatical material on a functional basis increases learners' speech activity and reduces the frequency of grammatical errors. These findings further confirm the effectiveness of the communicative approach in foreign language instruction [5].

Comparative analysis with existing approaches demonstrates that many traditional textbooks present grammatical material in a systematic yet excessively complex manner from the learner's perspective. Although grammatical rules are often organized in a logically sequential order, their communicative value is not always adequately taken into consideration. As a consequence, learners may acquire theoretical knowledge of grammatical rules while still experiencing considerable difficulty applying them in real communicative situations. The approach proposed in the present study seeks to eliminate this shortcoming by interpreting grammar not as an end in itself, but rather as a means of communication [6]. From this perspective, grammatical instruction should serve the broader purpose of enabling meaningful interaction rather than merely ensuring the memorization of formal structures.

The results of the study also demonstrate the significance of a corpus-based approach in determining grammatical minimums. By identifying the grammatical constructions most frequently used in authentic language practice, it becomes possible to select those units that are genuinely necessary for learners. Such an approach contributes to the optimization of instructional curricula and improves the overall efficiency of language teaching. Moreover, because corpus-based selection relies on real language usage rather than purely theoretical grammatical descriptions, its practical effectiveness is considerably higher [7]. This allows instructional materials to reflect contemporary communicative realities and increases learners' exposure to naturally occurring language patterns.

Another important aspect of the study concerns the necessity of applying a differential approach in the determination of grammatical minimums. Taking into account the linguistic background of each learner group constitutes a crucial factor in designing effective grammatical instruction. A grammatical minimum model developed specifically for English-speaking learners may not be fully appropriate for learners from other linguistic backgrounds. Typological similarities and differences between languages significantly influence the process of grammatical acquisition, the types of errors learners produce, and the degree of difficulty associated with particular grammatical structures. Therefore, it would be advisable for future research to develop separate grammatical minimum systems tailored to learners from different language groups. Such differentiated models would contribute to more effective language instruction by taking into consideration learners' specific linguistic and cognitive characteristics.

However, the study also possesses certain limitations. In particular, the pedagogical observations were conducted within a relatively limited group of participants. Furthermore, it was not possible to carry out a full-scale experimental assessment across all proficiency levels. For this reason, there remains a need for broader empirical investigations in future research. In particular, studies involving learners of different age groups and varying levels of language proficiency would allow for a more precise and comprehensive evaluation of the proposed approach. Such research could contribute to a deeper understanding of the relationship between grammatical acquisition, cognitive development, and communicative competence in the process of learning Uzbek as a foreign language.

It should therefore be emphasized that determining level-based grammatical minimums constitutes an important scientific and practical issue in teaching Uzbek as a foreign language. The approach proposed in this study makes it possible to distribute grammatical material in a systematic, functional, and learner-oriented manner. Such a model contributes to improving the effectiveness of Uzbek language instruction by ensuring that grammatical content corresponds to learners'

communicative needs and stages of language development. Moreover, the findings of the study may serve as a methodological foundation for the development of new curricula, instructional materials, and textbooks aimed at teaching Uzbek to foreign learners in a more efficient and scientifically grounded manner.

Conclusion. The present study once again confirms that determining level-based grammatical minimums in teaching Uzbek to English-speaking learners constitutes an important and highly relevant methodological issue. The findings of the research demonstrate that the traditional principle of presenting grammatical material “from simple to complex” is not sufficient when selecting and distributing grammar across proficiency levels. On the contrary, this process requires careful consideration of learners’ linguistic backgrounds, particularly the typological differences between English and Uzbek. In this respect, it was determined that the grammatical system of Uzbek, characterized by its agglutinative structure, creates distinctive challenges for English-speaking learners.

The results of the study further demonstrate the priority of the functional-semantic approach in determining grammatical minimums. In other words, grammatical units should be selected not according to their formal complexity, but according to their communicative function and practical relevance. Such an approach makes it possible to satisfy learners’ real communicative needs and to develop their ability to participate in communication more rapidly and effectively. In particular, simplifying grammatical material at the beginner levels and limiting instruction to only the most essential grammatical units significantly enhances the effectiveness of the learning process.

Furthermore, through comparative linguistic analysis and pedagogical observation, the study identified interference-related difficulties characteristic of English-speaking learners. These findings indicate the necessity of applying a differential approach in the development of grammatical minimums. The proposed model facilitates the gradual, systematic, and consistent acquisition of grammatical material while simultaneously reducing unnecessary cognitive overload for learners.

Overall, the findings of the study substantiate the necessity of developing a scientifically grounded system of grammatical minimums for teaching Uzbek as a foreign language. The proposed approach contributes to the improvement of curricula and textbooks, the optimization of the instructional process, and the effective development of learners’ communicative competence.

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Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
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